

Nestorian Christianity

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Chinese Nestorian Traditions, Nestorianism

Nestorian Christianity as a distinguished Christian group came into existence after the Christological movement that held the theological position initially developed by Nestorius (4/5 CE). Nestorius considered Christ the Son of God and Christ the son of Mary as two separate persons with two natures rather than one person having human and divine nature. That Christological teaching was officially condemned by the Council of Ephesus in 431. The Council of Ephesus anathema led to the separation of the early Church, development of the Nestorian doctrine and ultimately initiated the process of creating the so-called Church of the East. The teaching of the Church of the East as it developed throughout history should be distinguished from the initial Nestorian teaching. Theological differences quickly had political and socio-cultural implications at the global level (relationship with the Western Church as well as other Christian communities in the East). Historically speaking, Nestorian Christians played an important role in bringing Christianity to China as well as other regions like Mongolia and India. The historical timeline of Nestorian Christianity depends on the region, socio-cultural setting and date of missionary penetration. The bilingual (Chinese-Syriac) Nestorian stele (8th ct) from Xian witnesses to the early 7th century presence of Christians in the area. Nestorian Christians also reached India, and interacted with many other groups as Mongols, Turks, and Uigurs. Members of the Nestorian community played an important role during the Islamic period when they translated many works by Aristotle into Arabic (e.g. Timothy I). Modern Assyrian Church of the East is the successor of medieval Nestorian Christians, but its doctrine today should not be identified with Nestorius. After the disintegration of the Mongolian Empire during the 14th century, the Church of the East faced rapid decline. In the aftermath of these events, the presence of Nestorian Christianity was mainly reduced to India and Mesopotamia. During the 16th century, some members of the community united with the Roman Catholic Church and were named Chaldeans, whereas those who did not unite with the RCC became known as Assyrians. Nestorian Christians faced persecutions in Persia during the 6th century, but flourished in China (7-10th ct), and was also well received during the medieval Mongolian period.

Date Range: 431 CE - 1500 CE

Region: Nestorian Christianity

Region tags: Asia, South Asia, Southeast Asia, Syria, Arabian Gulf, Asia Minor, India, India, China

Nestorian Christianity at its greatest extent during the Middle Ages. The members of the community did not reach every region/place, but were present in many places covered by that map.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Budge, E.A.W., *The Monks of Kùblâi Khân, Emperor of China: or, The history of the life and travels of Rabban Sâwmâ, ... and Markôs who as Mâr Yahbh-Allâhâ III became Patriarch of the Nestorian Church in Asia* (London, 1928)

- Source 2: Moule, A.C., *Christians in China before the year 1550* (London, 1930)
- Source 3: Mingana, A., 'The Early Spread of Christianity in Central Asia and the Far East', *Bulletin of the John Rylands Library* 9 (1925) 297-371
- Source 1: Stewart, J., *Nestorian Missionary Enterprise: The Story of a Church on Fire* (Edinburgh, 1928)
- Source 2: Nau, F., 'L'expansion nestorienne en Asie', *Annales du Musée Guimet* 40 (1913) 193-388.
- Source 3: Pelliot, P., *L'inscription Nestorienne de Si-ngan-fou* (Kyoto/Paris, 1996)
- Source 1: Baumer, Christoph, *Frühes Christentum zwischen Euphrat und Jangtse. Eine Zeitreise entlang der Seidenstrasse zur Kirche des Ostens*. Stuttgart: Urachhaus, 2005.
- Source 2: Berti, Vittorio, "Les évêques de l'Église de Perse face au pouvoir séculier (Ve-VIIIe siècle)", Pages 123-145 in *L'évêque de Cour. Figure politique, figure polémique*. Edited by Destephen, Sylvain. Paris: Hermann, 2017.
- Source 3: Browne, Lawrence E., *The Eclipse of Christianity in Asia from the Time of Mohammed till the Fourteenth Century*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1933.
- Source 1: Nicolini-Zani, Matteo, "Il cristianesimo nella Cina dei Tang di fronte alla diversità religiosa", Pages 239-248 in *La Storia delle religioni e la sfida dei pluralismi. Atti del Convegno della Società Italiana di Storia delle Religioni - Roma, Sapienza, 8-9 aprile 2016*. Edited by Botta, Sergio and Ferrara, Marianna and Saggiaro, Alessandro. Quaderni di SMSR 18. Brescia: Morcelliana, 2017.
- Source 2: Spuler, Bertold, "Syrisches Christentum in Vorderasien und Südindien", *Saeculum* 32 (1981): 242-254.
- Source 1: Camelot, Thomas, "De Nestorius à Eutychès. L'opposition de deux christologies", Pages 213-242 in *Das Konzil von Chalkedon: Geschichte und Gegenwart*. Edited by Grillmeier, Alois and Bacht, Heinrich. Würzburg: Echter Verlag, 1951.
- Source 2: Baumstark, Anton, *Geschichte der syrischen Literatur, mit Ausschluss der christlich-palästinensischen Texte*. Bonn: A. Marcus und E. Weber, 1922.
- Source 3: Baum, Wilhelm, "Die Mongolen und das Christentum", Pages 13-52 in *Caucasus during the Mongol Period - Der Kaukasus in der Mongolenzeit*. Edited by Tubach, Jürgen and Vashalomidze, G. Sophia and Zimmer, Manfred. Wiesbaden: Reichert Verlag, 2012.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://gedsh.bethmardutho.org/Nestorianism>
- Source 1 Description: A good and short description of theological implications
- Source 2 URL: <https://gedsh.bethmardutho.org/entry/Nestorius?fq=fq-Browse:Browse;N;>
- Source 2 Description: a short biography of Nestorius
- Source 3 URL: <https://gedsh.bethmardutho.org/entry/Church-of-the-East?fq=fq-Browse:Browse;C;>
- Source 3 Description: a short history of the Church of the East

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general

populace)

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Rai9uoDZV2s>

– Source 1 Description: The lecture by Frances Woods "From Buddhism to Nestorian Christianity: The importance of the Silk Roads in the movement of ideas and religions across Central Asia"

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8o4j5xrIJLM>

– Source 2 Description: the video gives a good insight into theological disputes and differences between Nestorius and Cyril

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: http://www.nestorian.org/nestorian_theology.html

– Source 1 Description: A brief and clear outline of Nestorian theology

– Source 1 URL: http://nestorian.org/book_of_marganitha_part_i.html

– Source 1 Description: Book of Marganitha translated into English. One of the most important documents for understanding Nestorian theology in the Middle Ages

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Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

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General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Since it is not possible to precisely trace the travels of early Nestorians, it is also not possible to trace their cultural and religious contact with others. What we know is that there were bishoprics in Syria, Armenia, Persia, Arabia, Halvan, Herat, Merv, Tashkent, Samarkand, Baluk, Kashgar, Malabar in India and Hsi'en-fu in China. The Nestorians were certainly well spread, but not always with the intention to proselyte or to interact with others for religious purposes. They just coexisted with other religious groups. The social diversity provided by trade between Mesopotamia and Asia explains the mixing of religious concepts and cultural practices that led to religious and political syncretism. We have some more data from the later (Mongolian) period. Interaction of Nestorian Christians with members of other religious communities was especially visible in the Mongolian concept of ruling in the thirteenth century. To give an example, Khans were mainly of Shamanistic and Buddhist religious conviction, and were tolerant towards other religious groups. It was not unusual that Nestorian Christians were employed and respected by the Mongol rulers.

Reference: Tang, Li. *A Study of the History of Nestorian Christianity in China and Its Literature in Chinese*. Peter Lang, 2004.

https://books.google.com/books/about/A_Study_of_the_History_of_Nestorian_Chri.html?hl=&id=kLKKQgAACAAJ

Reference: Klimkeit, H. J., and I. Gillman. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Curzon Press, 1998.

Reference: Houston, G W.. "An Overview of Nestorians in Inner Asia". *Central Asiatic Journal* 24, no. 1/2 (June 1, 1980): 60-68.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: It depends on the region. For example, in China and Mongolia it was competitive in a way, but not violent. Nestorian Christians could peacefully (I mean without physical violence/threats) coexist during the Tang period in China, or during the Mongolian period later on. There were periods (for example during the Sung dynasty) when Christianity was not welcomed in China, but there was no physical violence - as far as we can see from the official records. It was rather diplomatic and cultural. The only condition for peaceful coexistence, especially during the Mongolian period, was that a religious group (including Christians) in the Empire respects the leader and pray for him. On the other hand, Nestorian Christians suffered under the Seljuks. The gradual increase of Turkish Islam in central Asia was caused by the disintegration of the Mongol Empire. The threat that the Western (Catholic) Church of the 13th century felt about the arrival of Mongols to Europe, was actually more political than religious, and the relationship between Catholics in Europe and Nestorians in Asia should be understood from that perspective as well.

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↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: There are some vessels that witness to the relation between Nestorian Christian messages and Buddhist art. There is also a characteristic piece of Sogdian Christian art on which Mary, the mother of God is not depicted. This fact could serve as a proof of Nestorian Christian doctrine because Nestorius considered Mary to be the mother of Christ (christotokos), not the mother of God (theotokos). On the other side, according to Lala Comneno, the pre-Islamic artistic and architectural remains in Central Asia constitute a patrimony without heirship.

Reference: Tang, Li. *A Study of the History of Nestorian Christianity in China and Its Literature in Chinese*. Peter Lang, 2004.

https://books.google.com/books/about/A_Study_of_the_History_of_Nestorian_Chri.html?hl=&id=kLKKQgAACAAJ.

Reference: Joachim, Hans Klimkeit. "Christian-buddhist Encounter in Medieval Central Asia". In *The Cross and the Lotus: Christianity and Buddhism in Dialogue*, 11-23. Motilal Banarsidass Publ., 1985.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: Christian conversion is treated neutrally by the locals. For example, many members of the nomadic peoples like Dailamites and Gilanians who lived near the Caspian Sea converted to Christianity. Some Nestorian Christians also adhered to Shamanism. However, during the Islamic period converting to Christianity was regarded as a threat to the Islamic rule (e.g. the Seljuks).

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↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: Not in China and Mongolia, but yes under the Seljuks.

Reference: Young, John M. L.. *By Foot to China: Mission of the Church of the East, to 1400*. Radio Press, 1984.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Reference: Cary-Elwis, C.. *China and the Cross: A Survey of Missionary History*. P. J. Kenedy & Sons, 1957.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

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Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: Baptism is required to become a (Nestorian) Christian, and in that respect, the answer is 'yes'. There is a nice story in the *Ecclesiastical Chronicle* by Barhebraeus about baptism: "When he promised him that he would become a lamb in the Christian sheepfold, he directed him and led him to salvation; and when he reached his tents in safety, he summoned the Christian merchants who were there, and discussed with them the question of faith, and they answered him that this could not be accomplished except through baptism. He took a Gospel from them, and lo he is worshipping it every day, and now he has summoned me to repair to him, or to send him a priest to baptise him"

Reference: Malek, R.. *Jingjiao: The Church of the East in China and in Central Asia*. Sankt Augustin, 2006.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Notes: Mainly because of the baptism requirement that is distinguished from birth. The people get baptized later (the age can vary) during the baptismal ceremony. Some liturgical books and homilies witness to the liturgical environment of the practice. For example, there was a special baptismal liturgy not necessarily connected with the celebration of the eucharist. Many of these rituals are preserved in Syriac but were also translated into Sogdian (the manuscripts were discovered in Turfan).

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: If the family and relatives are already members of the community, then the children naturally become members as well. Personal choice refers to those who decide to convert and to get baptized. For example, in the Thomas of Marga's Book of Governors, there is a description of the work of the Metropolitan of Gilan and Dailan, Subhailishu who is told to have "taught and baptized many towns and numerous villages, and brought them to the teaching of the divine life."

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

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↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: Religious affiliation is done by baptism, regardless of social status. For example, members of the Turkic speaking Ongud house/tribe (13th ct) had to be baptized although some of them were highly ranked in the Mongol society and firm adherents of Nestorianism.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Notes: There is no specific age for getting baptized. Usually, adults got baptized in the Nestorian community. For example, the *Chronica Minora*, which is a collection of anonymous writings from the 7th century says that one of the kings converted to Christianity with all his army: "When the king saw what Saint Elijah did, he fell down and worshipped him, and he was converted with all his army." There is also a possibility that the children were baptized at the early stage. For example, there is also evidence from the area of Karakorum that all male children baptized later received consecration as priests.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

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↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: Males and females are equally required to be baptized in order to become members of the Nestorian community. There is no evidence whatsoever that the membership was assigned by gender.

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↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: The baptism occupied the most important place in the Nestorian Christian community. It was usually performed on a certain number of people who wanted to join the group. The ritual was usually held around Easter time, but not exclusively.

Reference: Arangassery, Lonappan. *Holy Baptism in the Syriac East*. St Ephrem's Theological College, 2010.

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↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Specific to this answer:

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Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Proselytizing is done by preaching and based on the inner conviction of the importance of salvation. Recruitment is not based on violence or external pressure. For example, the Book of Governors by Thomas of Marga witnesses: "these were the Bishops who preached the teaching of Christ in those countries of the Dailamites and Gilanians, and the rest of the savage peoples beyond them, and planted in them the light of the truth of the Gospel of our Lord. They evangelized them and they baptized them, worked miracles and showed prodigies, and the news of their exploits reached the farthest points of the East". Also, Bar Hebraeus says in the Syrian Chronicle: "In this very day a nation from the nations of the Turks inhabiting the interior of the country towards the East, called Kerit, believed in Christ, and were instructed in the faith and baptised through a miracle that happened to their king."

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. Christians in Asia Before 1500. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

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Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: The Nestorian stele from Xi'an (781 CE) claims: "The Emperor sent the Chancellor, Duke Fang Hsuan-ling, to lead an escort to the western suburb, and received him as guest in the Palace. The Scriptures were translated in the Royal Library, and their doctrine examined in the Private Apartments. Knowing full well that it was right and true, the Emperor expressly commanded its propagation". Furthermore, the Nestorian communities in China were all subordinate to a Nestorian metropolitan residing in Khan Baliq, which was raised to metropolitan status in the late 13th century. That indicates there was political support in the Mongol period. For the earliest period of Nestorian presence in Asia, we have much less evidence.

Reference: Scott, David. "Christian Responses to Buddhism in Pre-medieval Times". *Numen* 32, no. 1 (September 30, 1985): 88-100.

Reference: Nau, F.. "L'expansion Nestorienne En Asie". *Annales Du Musée Guimet* 40 (December 13, 1913).

Reference: Foster, J.. *The Church of the T'ang Dynasty*. Society for Promoting Christian Knowledge, 1930.

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Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Not formally. However, consequences of a denunciation of faith are tied to social networks and social belonging. There is a story about a Nestorian king George who took Lesser Orders of the Latins (i.e. the Western Roman Catholic Church) and was then accused of apostasy by other Nestorians.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. Christians in Asia Before 1500. Routledge, 2013.

<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

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Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

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Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no precise research on that question. In addition, historical texts do not seem to have been interested in this kind of data. However, they occasionally indicate local numbers. For example, the data given by Mari ibn Suleiman and Barhebraeus suggest that a Turkic king together with 200,000 subjects converted to Christianity.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Reference: Tang, Li. *A Study of the History of Nestorian Christianity in China and Its Literature in Chinese*. Peter Lang, 2004.

https://books.google.com/books/about/A_Study_of_the_History_of_Nestorian_Chri.html?hl=&id=kLKKQgAACA AJ.

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Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The most known translation of the Bible that was used by Nestorian Christians is the Peshitta. It is a Syriac version of the Old and the New Testament(s) most probably translated in Edessa before the 4th century CE. Although there is strong evidence that many references from the Peshitta can be found already in the early period of Syriac literature (e.g. biblical narratives attested in the 4th century works

by Ephrem and Aphrahat), it is only in the 9th century when the corpus became known under that name. Concerning the presence of Nestorian Christians in Asia, there is a story about an encounter between a Frenchman, William Bouchier, and the Great Khan Mangu. Mangu has visited the Nestorian Church and examined the Frenchman's Bible noticing that they did not follow the same scripture. Apparently, the Bouchier's Bible was textually different from the Nestorian Scriptures.

Reference: Weitzman, Michael P.. *The Syriac Version of the Old Testament: An Introduction*. Cambridge University Press, 1999.

Specific to this answer:

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Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The translation is made from Hebrew (the Old Testament) and Greek (the New Testament). The earliest manuscript we have today at disposition is from the 5th century. Despite the written evidence, there was also a very strong tradition of oral transmission.

Reference: Joosten, Jan. *The Syriac Language of the Peshitta and Old Syriac Versions of Matthew*. BRILL, 1996.

https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Syriac_Language_of_the_Peshitta_and.html?hl=&id=RrLe3e6Hx-QC.

Reference: Dirksen, Peter Berend, and Arie van der Kooij. *The Peshitta as a Translation*. BRILL, 1995. https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Peshitta_As_a_Translation.html?hl=&id=KouWwyV5vScC.

Reference: Bauscher, David. *The Peshitta Holy Bible Translated*. Lulu.com, 2019. https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Peshitta_Holy_Bible_Translated.html?hl=&id=KmWPDwAAQBAJ.

Reference: Falla, Terry C.. *A Key to the Peshitta Gospels*. BRILL, 1991. https://books.google.com/books/about/A_Key_to_the_Peshitta_Gospels.html?hl=&id=ZzmOEjT4e54C.

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Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: There is a strong oral culture of transmitting beliefs and values. The Scriptures in Syriac were known throughout the Central Asia. Many passages were used in the Eucharist and the hourly prayers. They were not only used by Syrian speaking Christians from Western Asia, but also by Central and East Asians. The liturgical context also suggests that many passages were memorized and orally transmitted.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

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Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: The most known and the earliest legend about the origin of the Syriac Bible is that it was translated under the king Abgar. The legend is not historically true, but it witnesses to the early existence of the Scriptures translated into Syriac. The Peshitta (Syriac) version of the Bible was already used in the commentaries by Ephrem and Aphrahat (4th CE). In the later period, Nestorian Christians brought the Scriptures to China. The Nestorian stele from Xi'an (781 CE) witnesses to that: "The Syrian (Ta Ch'in) Bishop (Great Virtue) Alopen, bringing scriptures and images from afar, has come to present them in our Capital"

Reference: Ramelli, Ilaria. Possible Historical Traces in the Doctrina Addai. Gorgias Press, 2009. https://books.google.com/books/about/Possible_Historical_Traces_in_the_Doctri.html?hl=&id=mNj_QQAACAAJ.

Reference: Ellis, Ralph. Jesus, King of Edessa. Edfu Books, 2012. https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=-4HF9Sfsw_cC.

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Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: The Nestorian Christian community believed that the Scriptures were revealed by God the Father to Moses in the form of the Pentateuch, and later through Jesus (and Holy Spirit) to the apostles. As stated above, the Syriac community created their own version of biblical narratives which was used in the Asian environment. Understanding of the Scriptures was based on belief in resurrection (which is the message of Christianity) and also under local cultural and religious influences - Buddhism, Manichaeism, Chinese culture, and Islam.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. Christians in Asia Before 1500. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Reference: Lattimore, Owen. "Caravan Routes of Inner Asia: The Third "asia Lecture"". The Geographical Journal 72, no. 6 (December 15, 1928): 497-528.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: The Scriptures are both revealed and inspired. Since the central message of Christianity (including the Nestorian Christians) is the incarnation, the Scriptures are regarded as divinely revealed and inspired, but they are not as central as the message of God's incarnation.

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↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

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↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

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↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

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Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: There are Nestorian monasteries like the Ta Qin in Shaanxi province in Wuchun (China). The monastery was built in the 7th century, has a distinctive pagoda typical for that region. The monastery later became first a Buddhist, and then a Taoist shrine.

Reference: Tang, Li, and Dietmar W. Winkler. *From the Oxus River to the Chinese Shores*. LIT Verlag Münster, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=VYaMuV3N5vUC>.

Reference: Johnson, Scott Fitzgerald. *The Oxford Handbook of Late Antiquity*. Oxford University Press, 2012. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=hOgBBx-ljrMC>.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

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Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Notes: Mainly churches and monasteries.

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↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: In the Ongut area there is a number of Nestorian tombstones (13th and 14th century) ornamented by crosses and leaves

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Notes: For example, a Nestorian cemetery (14th ct) near Issik-Köl lake.

Reference: Dani, Ahmad Hasan. *History of Civilizations of Central Asia*. Motilal Banarsidass Publ., 1999. https://books.google.com/books/about/History_of_Civilizations_of_Central_Asia.html?hl=&id=DguGWPOvGY8C.

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: There are many Nestorian monasteries in China. For example, the saint Mar Sergius was a very popular saint in China to whom various monasteries were dedicated. Each monastery also had a church (i.e. temple).

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge,

2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: Cultural exchanges and influences as well as conversion stories witness to different practices. For example, Mari ibn Suleiman (12th ct) in the Book of the Tower mentions that the king who converted to Christianity set up a pavilion to take the place of an altar, in which was a cross and a Gospel.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. Christians in Asia Before 1500. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Notes: Basically crosses.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: When they can - the people gather in churches, monasteries, and cemeteries.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Only religious public space

– Some public spaces

Notes: For example, there is a mural painting in the Nestorian church in the Turfan oasis at Kocho showing a Persian or Sogdian priest addressing an assembly of two Turks and a Chinese lady.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. Christians in Asia Before 1500. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people,

general populace)

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Notes: For example, it is visible in fusion of Nestorian art with other religious traditions and cultures. In some cases, the style is similar to the Buddhist way of painting Bodhisattva's figures.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: The figure of Jesus. The famous example is the Nestorian painting of Jesus Christ from the 9th century (China).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

Notes: Usually the cross, and very often the cross on lotus symbol. The famous example is the Nestorian stele from Xi'an (781 CE)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Nestorian Christianity also adopted elements from Mahayana Buddhism. For example, Jesus is sometimes depicted rowing the boat of mercy to the sky.

Reference: Rosenkranz, Gerhard. *Die Älteste Christenheit in China in Den Quellenschriften Der Nestorianer-texte Der Tang-dynastie*. Berlin: Ostasien-Mission, 1939.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Notes: The cross, which had the figure for ten in Chinese script, had both anthropological and cosmological connotations. It was an indicator of the four quarters (the zenith and nadir= and also an image of the human body (Jesus).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: For example, a female figure from the T'ang dynasty, in a Christian Church at Qočo (9th ct)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: For example, during the Sasanian period, Peter's denial of Christ was a theme of specific significance to Christians under non-Christian rulers. Or, in Sogdian art, the

narrative about Abraham's sacrifice of Isaac.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The spirit-body distinction is based on the belief that God as an invisible being took a human shape. Furthermore, discussions of the qualities of God are linked with the discussions of the nature of the human soul and body. There is a strong spirit-body distinction that is based on the relationship between the immortality of the soul and five senses of the human body.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in the sense that spirit is considered stronger as body. Spirit is the one to dominate the body. This is based on the general Christian principle deriving from Mt 26:41 "The spirit is willing, but the flesh is weak"

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Nestorian Christians believed that salvation implies a new creation which implies the resurrection from the dead - the most important Christian message. An interesting fact is that some pieces of Sogdian Christian art testify to the influence of Christians in the cultural life of Sogdiana. Some of them depict scenes related to the death and resurrection of Christ. Such art also testifies to the belief in after-life by the members of the Nestorian Christian community.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013.

<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Reference: Klimkeit, Hans-Joachim. *Religionsbegegnung Und Kulturaustausch in Asien*. Otto Harrassowitz Verlag, 2002.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Religionsbegegnung_und_Kulturaustausch_i.html?hl=&id=x8b65_oP7g4C.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: There is only one life and one process of dying after which one is awarded by eternal salvation or damnation. Therefore, there is no idea of reincarnation in the Nestorian Christian doctrine despite for example intensive Christian-Buddhist dialogue in Central Asia. They lived together and were in constant interaction. The result of these interactions are most visible in art. Although Christian and Buddhist groups exchanged motives and cultural heritage, the core beliefs were not affected.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Reference: Scott, David. "Christian Responses to Buddhism in Pre-medieval Times". *Numen* 32, no. 1 (July 18, 1985): 88-100.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: The corpses were buried in the ground during a specific ritual and prayers. The members of the community usually wear mourning garments for the funeral. John of Cora writes: "To his obsequies and burial there came a very great multitude of people, both Christians and pagans. And those pagans rent their mourning garments as their manner is; and both Christians and pagans devoutly laid hold of the clothes of the archbishop, and carried them off as relics with great reverence."

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Reference: Troll, Christian W.. "Die Chinamission Im Mittelalter". *Franziskanische Studien* 48 (June 15, 1966).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: Community members offer prayers for the soul of the dead; there are no co-sacrifices. There is a practice of supplicatory prayers to the Lord God, the saviour for those in need and suffering, the one granting remission of sins.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Reference: Klimkeit, Hans-Joachim. *Religionsbegegnung Und Kulturaustausch in Asien*. Otto Harrassowitz Verlag, 2002. https://books.google.com/books/about/Religionsbegegnung_und_Kulturaustausch_i.html?hl=&id=x8b65_oP7g4C.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: Indifference to for example the Egyptian practice from pharaonic times, the people are buried without any additional goods in the grave. The graves themselves are decorated with inscriptions surrounding the sign of the cross that marks the people were Christians. For example, to the south of Lake Balkash around 600 Christian tombstones were found. Many of them had dates inscribed.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: For example, there is a testimony by John of Cora who writes that even pagans went to burial ceremonies of the deceased Christians: "And those pagans rent their mourning garments as their manner is: and both Christians and pagans devoutly laid hold of the clothes of the archbishop, and carried them off as relics with great reverence... and they still visit the place of his internment with very great devotion." There was also a special ritual for burial of priests. One among other supplications for the deceased priests say: "Bitter, O our brother, is thy death, and sad is the day of thy separation from us; for death took thee suddenly away, and hath shut thee up in the darkness of the grave. Christ give thee bliss with all the priests thy associates, and to all who have assembled at thy funeral may bliss be given with thee in the kingdom."

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Reference: Asimov, M. S., and Clifford Edmund Bosworth. *History of Civilizations of Central Asia*. Motilal Banarsidass Publ., 1992. https://books.google.com/books/about/History_of_Civilizations_of_Central_Asia.html?hl=&id=ELrRrOL8UoC.

Reference: Badger, George Percy. *The Nestorians and Their Rituals*. Vol. 2. Forgotten Books, 2018.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Notes: There is no systematic research on that question. It is probable cenotaphs existed since they are mentioned in some sources. For example, Barhebraeus says that a celebrated Nestorian physician obtained an order from the Caliph requesting the Sultan of Egypt to send the bones of a prelate to Bagdad. This was prevented by the officiousness of a Nestorian monk who claimed that he had a vision in which it was revealed to him that the Jacobites wasted their fury on a cenotaph and that the resting place of Nestorius was unknown to a mortal man.

Reference: Neale, John Mason. *A History of the Holy Eastern Church*. Oxford, Cambridge: J.H. Parker, Macmillan and co., 1847.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: For example, a cemetery near the Issik-Kol Lake (14th ct). There is also a graveyard near Pishpek where about 3000 people must have been buried. The inscriptions found at that cemetery reveal the use of the Sasanian calendar and the Turkish cycle of twelve years. That indicates the presence of a strong Nestorian tradition in the area.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: In a niche of the rock, an early burial with remains of Nestorian Christians was discovered in the Chinese province of Henan in the Longmen grotto near the town of Loyang. A cross is engraved in a niche near the site where human bones and ashes were laid. That might suggest that members of the same family were buried there. However, that place should not be considered as a tomb-crypt in the strict sense of the word.

Reference: www.orthochristian.com. "Burial of Nestorian Christians Discovered in China". [www.orthochristian.com](http://www.orthochristian.com/67738.html), January 20, 2014. <http://www.orthochristian.com/67738.html>.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Notes: it is not an excluded option, but there is no evidence for that. Formal burials are usually held at graveyards.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: God in the form of Trinity is within the Nestorian community considered as a supernatural, eternal, and powerful being. That being answers to prayers and is expected to intervene in specific circumstances. For example, Nestorians used spells against diseases. These spells reveal the relationship between medicine, magic, and religion. The use of spells also suggests that members of the community believed in the supreme and supernatural being who is able to resolve all the problems.

Reference: Panegyres, Konstantine. "Notes on a Nestorian Spell Against Headaches". *Mnemosyne* 69, no. 3 (June 15, 2016).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: As in other Christian communities, the supreme God is believed to monitor human beings. Members of the community believe in the constant presence of God who watches their actions in order to grant them with salvation or punish eternally.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: Since Christian God Jesus was a human being, he is represented anthropologically. God the Father is usually depicted as a human being and the Holy Spirit in the form of fire. These representations are based on reading the Scriptures and theological traditions.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: Based on the Christian reading of Genesis 1, Christian God (Trinity) is held as a sky deity.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: The community members also believe in the existence of hell. Hell is the place for the wicked souls. God is the lord of hell as well primarily because he is considered as the creator of everything visible and invisible. The domination over hell, however, belongs to Satan and demons.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– Yes

Notes: God is considered as a king in a metaphorical way. Jesus is considered a king of life.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common

people, general populace)

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: The earthly monarchs (or kings) are considered as the ones receiving the power and support from the supreme God but are not considered as a manifestation or emanation of the high god (e.g. Genghis Khan). The main reason for that is the belief that the only king to be considered as God is Jesus himself. To consider any monarch as god would be against the Christian doctrine.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: That would be against the Christian message and ethics. God does not look at the social status.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: God (Trinity) is considered as a perfect, omnipotent being. He is considered as unquestionably good even when he punishes the people for their sins.

Reference: Beulay, Robert. "La Beauté De Dieu: Transcendance Et Tendresse Chez Jean De Dalyatha". Carmel 46 (June 18, 1987).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Immutability, Providence, Veracity, Righteousness, Holiness, Impassibility, Impeccability.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Since God (Trinity) is considered as the eternal creator of the world, he also has knowledge of everything that happens in the created world. Omniscience is also one of the attributes of Christian (Nestorian) God.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: Since God is considered as omniscient, he knows everything.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: There is no human action that God cannot see/be aware of. This is derived from the Christian (Nestorian) reading of the Psalms.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: God (Trinity) is the only supernatural being that can see inside the heart and mind. Other supernatural beings (angels, demons) can have knowledge of human actions to the extent God allows them to.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: God knows the future, but at the same time grants the free will to the creation. The future is causally dependent on the actions taken by human beings.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: God rewards for actions he considers good.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

— Yes

Notes: God punishes for actions he considers bad.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common
people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

— Yes

Notes: Although God is considered as good, his so-called positive emotions are reflected through the good behavior of human beings.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common
people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

— Yes

Notes: God shows the so-called negative emotions via punishments for sins of human beings. The most known example is the story of Noah's ark from Genesis 6. Community members are warned about God's punishment through readings of the Holy Scriptures.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common
people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

— No

Notes: Since God does not have a physical body, he does not feel hunger. As incarnate God, Jesus felt hunger but with his human, not divine nature.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: God can sometimes speak or reveal things in dreams. For example, Yahbh-Allaha had two dreams in which it was indicated that he was marked out by God for promotion to the highest position in the Nestorian Church.

Reference: Budge, E. A. Wallis. "The Monks of Kublai Khan Emperor of China". www.aina.org, n.d.. <http://www.aina.org/books/mokk/mokk.htm>.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: Communication is implicit. The people believe in God's will, and therefore interpret their actions as God's will. There is no explicit verbal communication.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: Although priests and monks are considered as chosen people, God does not exclusively communicate his will through them. He can reveal his will to anyone in the society.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

Notes: Whilst the body is considered mortal, the community members believe in the eternal existence of the soul. In that respect, they believe that the spirit of the dead is alive, but they (spirits) are not present.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people,
general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the community believes in the existence of angels, but the supreme power is attributed to the triune God only. Angels were examples of purity to follow, especially in the monastic way of living. Monks used to abstain from sleep, food, and sexual life in order to constantly praise God like angels. Angels are considered as perfect examples to follow in the spiritual life, but are not worshipped.

Reference: Thomas, Huw. "In Search of Ancient Christianity: The Nestorian Caves of Tajikistan". www.rsaa.org.uk, n.d.. <https://rsaa.org.uk/blog/2016/02/02/in-search-of-ancient-christianity-the-nestorian-caves-of-tajikistan/>.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people,
general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: There is no record of private apparitions of supernatural beings. However, the community believed that angels can appear to humans because of the annunciation story from Luke 1:26-38: "In the sixth month the angel Gabriel was sent by God to a town in Galilee called Nazareth, to a virgin engaged to a man whose name was Joseph, of the house of David. The virgin's name was Mary. And he came to her and said, "Greetings, favoured one! The Lord is with you." But she was much perplexed by his words and pondered what sort of greeting this might be. The angel said to her, "Do not be afraid, Mary, for you have found favour with God. And now, you will conceive in your womb and bear a son, and you will name him Jesus. He will be great, and will be called the Son of the Most High, and the Lord God will give to him the throne of his ancestor David. He will reign over the house of Jacob forever, and of his kingdom there will be no

end." Mary said to the angel, "How can this be, since I am a virgin?" The angel said to her, "The Holy Spirit will come upon you, and the power of the Most High will overshadow you; therefore the child to be born will be holy; he will be called Son of God. And now, your relative Elizabeth in her old age has also conceived a son; and this is the sixth month for her who was said to be barren. For nothing will be impossible with God." Then Mary said, "Here am I, the servant of the Lord; let it be with me according to your word." Then the angel departed from her."

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: They are not material beings. They are believed to have spiritual bodies.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: They act in the physical world if the supreme God (Trinity) allows them to do so.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: There is a belief in the existence of angels who are organized hierarchically. However, they are not considered as gods. Many Syriac writers, including the famous Jacob of Edessa commented on the existence and the role of angels. Evagrius Ponticus also influenced the Syriac understanding of angels via translations of his works into Syriac.

Reference: Greatrex, Marina. "The Angelology in the Hexaemeron of Jacob of Edessa". *Journal of the Canadian Society for Syriac Studies* 3 (June 15, 2004).

Reference: Muyldermans, Joseph. "Sur Les Seraphins Et Sur Les Chérubins D'evagre Le Pontique Dans Les Versions Syriaque Et Arménienne". *Le Muséon* 59 (June 15, 1946).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: Nestorian Christians are mainly concerned about ethical norms as outlined in the Bible (Syriac translation and versions in local languages) and practiced within the community. These norms and practices are considered as supernatural monitoring.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general)

populace)

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Nestorian Christians are concerned with ethical norms as outlined in the Bible and the local community. For example, they sometimes use conventional Buddhist or Taoist concepts to expound Christian doctrine.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: The Bible is the main source for ethical and moral instructions. Specific treatises exist as well in the form of biblical commentaries (e.g. commentaries by Ephrem, Aphrat, Narsai, Isaac of Nineveh, Jacob of Edessa. Greek authors like Theodore of Mopsuestia also had a significant influence upon the Eastern Syriac tradition). Lord Prayer also has a special place in ethical instructions and commentaries.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: As in other Christian communities, there is no animal sacrifice in the Nestorian rite. The only sacrifice is Jesus himself who is believed to have given his life for the people. The Eucharist is considered as the celebration of Jesus' sacrifice. Some texts from Turfan reflect monastic and eremitic ideals with an emphasis on fasting, penances as well as preparation for death and judgement. The centre of all these practices was the celebration of the liturgy, especially the Eucharist.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Reference: Stone, Darwell. *A History of the Doctrine of the Holy Eucharist*. Wipf and Stock Publishers, 2007. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=IMRLAwAAQBAJ>.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: Not to desecrate sacred places like churches and monasteries. Such an understanding of sacred places is more implicit than explicit. Namely, there is no evidence in Nestorian sources that would explicitly comment on for example Ezekiel 38-48, a passage that inter alia warns against desecrating objects. The members of the Nestorian Christian community have never turned churches or monasteries into something else. There is not yet a systematic study on that subject.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: not to desecrate sacred objects like crosses, Scriptures, statues, and the like. The only disrespect towards objects like these ones could have occasionally come from non-Christians. For example, when Marco Polo describes the Khan's court at Khan Baliq, he mentions a certain Nestorian Christian Naian who had been overcome by the ruler. When non-Christians made fun of the cross which that Nestorian had borne on his banner, the Khan rebuked them comforting the Christians, as their God had not helped a traitor.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: The supreme God cares about coherence of belief

Notes: God cares about the coherence of belief and inner disposition. The care is expressed in the Holy Scriptures (Bible).

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Murder is prohibited by the ten commandments (Ex 20 and Deut 5).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: Since murder of any human being is prohibited by the ten commandments (Ex 20 and Deut 5), that also includes members of other religions.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: Murder is prohibited by the ten commandments (Ex 20 and Deut 5), which also includes members of other polities. It is also hard to believe that Nestorians would murder members of other polities on the religious basis since the presence of Christianity in China is proved by consent of Chinese, Arabian, Syriac and Latin evidence. That also suggests their intense interaction. If a murder happened in some cases, it was not on the religious basis.

Reference: Takakusu, J. "The Name of "messiah" Found in a Buddhist Book: The Nestorian Missionary Adam, Presbyter, Papas of China, Translating a Buddhist Sutra". T'oung Pao 7, no. 5 (October 15, 1896).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: Adultery is prohibited - as in the ten commandments (Ex 20 and Deut 5), Heb 13.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: Incest is prohibited - e.g. Leviticus 18

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: e.g. homosexual practices or other "sexual perversions" as prohibited in the Bible.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Lying is prohibited - Ten commandments (Ex 20 and Deut 5): You shall not bear false witness against your neighbor

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: once given, vows and oaths are to be kept, otherwise, they are considered as a sin (e.g. Deuteronomy 23:21 - "If you make a vow to the Lord your God, you shall not delay fulfilling it, for the Lord your God will require it of you, and you will be guilty of sin")

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: Laziness is considered as negative: Proverbs 10:4 "Lazy hands make for poverty, but diligent hands bring wealth"

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: Doing sorcery is prohibited. Leviticus 19:31 "Do not turn to mediums or necromancers; do not seek them out, and so make yourselves unclean by them: I am the Lord your God"

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: Respect for elders is explicitly focused on parents and family: Ten commandments (Ex 20 and Deut 5): honor your father and your mother

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: Gossip and evil tongue are regarded as evil: James 3:8 "No human being can tame the tongue. It is a restless evil, full of deadly poison"

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: The Bible forbids stealing and requires the wrongdoer to make the repair. Leviticus 19:11: "Do not steal"

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: Nestorian Christian practice is more focused on inner disposition than external correctness of ritual observance, although the latter is also important (frequent practice of prayer and Eucharist)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: yes, but is focused more on inner disposition than on external observation of ritual rules.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: There is a strong feeling of duty to preach the Gospel to all men. However, these practices were not violent. If there is pressure, it is more socio-cultural.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: The idea of economic fairness and sharing property is explicitly encouraged. Acts 2:44 "And all the believers met together in one place and shared everything they had"

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: For example, some groups of Nestorian Christians used to wash their lower parts before entering a church.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: God punishes sin if the person does not follow the moral principles of conduct as set out in the Bible, especially in the teaching of Jesus. He (Jesus) is considered as consubstantial with the human being in everything except the sin. One of the early fathers of the Nestorian Church, Babai the Great, in his Book of the Union argues that "There are two divine and human natures united in Christ. Therefore there is only one son and one union person". Jesus is also believed as being a perfect example of a human being and therefore a teacher of how to avoid sin and do good.

Reference: Babai the Great. Liber De Unione. Edited by A. Vaschalde. Louvain, 1915.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: God generally punishes sins. Sometimes the cause is explicitly presumed. For example, if someone knows (s)he has done something wrong and then something bad happens to him/her, then the person will attribute that action to God; but sometimes, causality can't be traced, it's just presumed to depend on the case. Since Nestorians also mixed magic, medicine, spells and beliefs it is hard to trace the first responsibility for the punishment. God is generally presumed as the main punishment actor.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: Nestorian Christians did believe in the existence of angels but did not attribute supreme controlling powers to them when it comes to punishments of sins. In 1918 in the area of Yangzhou some farmers unearthed a Nestorian gravestone which bears an illustration of a cross flanked by angels and two inscriptions - a Chinese text and a Turkish text in Syriac script. That monument bears witness that Nestorians believed in the existence of other supernatural beings except God himself.

Reference: Ertl, Thomas. "Repercussions from the Far East: A Comparison of the Catholic and Nestorian Presence in China", n.d.. <https://heiup.uni-heidelberg.de/journals/index.php/transcultural/article/view/19773/17230>.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Notes: Punishment of sins is not causal in the sense that it is predictable. Negative life

events can be understood as a punishment for sins.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Acts 3:19 "Repent, therefore, and be converted, that your sins may be blotted out when the times of refreshing shall come from the presence of the Lord"

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: Those who sin are punished by death. Ezekiel 18:4 "Behold, all souls are mine; as the soul of the father, so also the soul of the son is mine: the soul that sins, it shall die."

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: 1 John 3:4 "Whoever commits sin transgresses also the law: for sin is the transgression of the law"

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done randomly:

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that the punishment is not predictable.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Eternal damnation and salvation are highly emphasized in discussions and preaching.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Romans 6:23 "For the wages of sin is death, but the gift of God is eternal life through Christ Jesus our Lord"

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Matthew 25:41 "Depart from me, you cursed, into the eternal fire prepared for the devil and his angels"

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Notes: After death, the soul is eternally rewarded or punished only once. There is no reincarnation.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Notes: There is no belief in multiple lives (there is no reincarnation). One is rewarded or punished after death.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: It is done through repenting and good deeds: Luke 15:7 "Just so, I tell you, there will be more joy in heaven over one sinner who repents than over ninety-nine righteous persons who need no repentance."

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: If behaved well, the main reward for a member of the community is eternal salvation after death.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Notes: Good deeds in earthly life are the cause of supernatural rewards.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: God is considered as the final judge.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

Notes: Eternal salvation is preached to those who behave well. Good behavior also includes observing group norms. So, implicitly yes - rewards or promises of rewards are done to enforce group norms.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done randomly:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Observing the commandments and good behavior in the community are rewarded in the afterlife in the form of eternal salvation. Rewards are provided by God-Trinity only.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: God is believed to give prosperity to those who observe the commandments. Supernatural rewards come in the form of health, good luck, political success, success in battle, and the like. Genghis Khan, for example, was considered as successful because of his belief to the supreme God (his mother was Nestorian.)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE
Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE
Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE
Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE
Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE
Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: For example, in Turkish languages used by Nestorian Christians, Jesus is called the Son of Heaven, King, Khan, Physician, and the King Messiah.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Notes: It is not known, but some texts (e.g. The Lord of the Universe's Discourse on Alms-giving) show the belief that the Messiah will come again to do curing for three and a half years.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: The Tachi'n Luminous Religion Sutra on the Origin of Origins depicts the Messiah as Saviour who sits on the throne of Precious Law surrounded by the Holy Clouds.

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

↳ Other purpose:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Notes: Not in theory, but yes in practice. There are no special social norms except those in the Bible, and regulations of Nestorian subgroups. For example, because of their different life-style, communities in monasteries across Asia will have a distinct understanding of social norms. Furthermore, members of the Nestorian community sometimes developed attitudes towards members of other religious groups. For example, one of the envoys by the Pope Innocent IV, John of Montecorvino, writes in 1305: "The Nestorians have grown so powerful in these parts that they have not allowed any Christians of another rite to have however small a chapel, nor to publish any other doctrine than the Nestorian".

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. Christians in Asia Before 1500. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: That also depends on the period. In environments where community was not appreciated within a larger society, there is a bigger distinction between conventional and moral than for example in societies where conventional and moral go more together. The latter was the case in the Mongolian period. Nestorian played an important role in the Mongol state as soldiers, officials, physicians and also, mothers and wives of some Mongol rulers were Nestorian. When it comes to the group itself, it is hard to trace a difference between conventional and moral.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present (but not emphasized)

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

Notes: The Nestorian stele from Xi'an (781) says: "The True Lord, unoriginated, tranquil and still, eternally abiding, in the beginning, He created, raised the earth and set up heaven". Moral norms are expressed with clarity, but emanate from the 'True Lord' whose descriptions are too metaphysical for lower-ranked members of the community.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus as 'the reason for Christianity' is a good example. He is both human and divine, and is understood as incarnate God.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of

anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society

Notes: In the hierarchy of the Nestorian Church, which were in accordance with the hierarchy of the angels, there were nine grades divided in three. However, moral norms apply to everyone on the scale.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Nestorian Church allowed marriage even for the Patriarch, archbishops, and bishops. They did not have problems with the recruitment of clergy, but other Christian denominations like for example Jacobites did. On the other hand, there were Nestorian monks that were engaged in education at the courts of Khans.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: Monogamy is required for both male and female members of the community.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Chastity is highly respected by certain members (monks) of the community.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: for example, Nestorian nuns expressed their sexual modesty with clothing.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: Bodily integrity is highly respected.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: It is not required, but some group members, especially monks, practice fasting. They usually abstain from meat.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: painful bodily alterations are opposed to the idea of bodily integrity which is highly respected.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory

painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Only Nestorian monks and nuns who by definition renounce material possessions. They also do not eat meat (and fish) and do not drink wine.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: There are around 500 books written in Syriac attested in China which were used in the Eucharist and the daily prayers, especially between the 9th and the 13th century. Participation in liturgy and prayers was required by the members.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: For example, Christian precepts for daily life as expressed in the ten commandments were connected with Chinese virtues like ancestor worship, piety, and loyalty to the Emperor. The ten commandments and the life of Jesus are explicated in Buddhist and Confucian terms to make them more understandable to the Chinese audience.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: Not officially, but conversions are quite often socially disrespected.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– I don't know

Notes: There were specific prayers as for rain for example, but it is not known if these were prayed in churches only, or also privately. An example of such a prayer "The water - thy symbol - let it fall down at thy command on our fields, and our earth chose (this) our desert (for your rain= through thy grace and have mercy upon us".

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. Christians in Asia Before 1500. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: Large-scale rituals are celebrations of Christmas and Easter. Baptism of new members of the community is usually celebrated around Easter.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In monasteries, the rituals (prayers) were held on daily basis. It is however not known what were the prayer intervals of the larger Nestorian population.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: they are mainly performed by priests and monks.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

Notes: not as a rule, but the customs of local communities are visible in Christian rituals. Aside from different social movements, there are also some interesting remarks that testify to the mixing of religious ideas and concepts. There are vessels that were found and that show a sort

of relation between Nestorian Christian messages and Buddhist art of Both India and the Silk Road

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Notes: Nestorian Christians are generally opposed to intoxicants like alcohol.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Notes: members become brothers and sisters in Christ - which is also common Christian terminology, not specifically Nestorian.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: Nestorian Christians were used to a royal/empire setting. They were mainly active in the Chinese

empire, Mongolian empire, Persian empire.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Reference: Mungello, David Emil. "Reinterpreting the History of Christianity in China". *The Historical Journal* 55, no. 2 (June 15, 2012).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although there is no evidence about formal famine relief, it is probable that some monks helped the people in towns like Kashgar on the southern Silk Route which were hit by war and famine.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes. For example, there is a story that a certain Russian helped a Franciscan monk (13th ct) when he was in need of food.

Reference: Klimkeit, Hans-Joachim. *Religionsbegegnung Und Kulturaustausch in Asien*. Otto Harrassowitz Verlag, 2002.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Religionsbegegnung_und_Kulturaustausch_i.html?hl=&id=x8b65_oP7g4C.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: Not institutionalized, but it is practiced since Christianity encourages helping others. For example, Rabban Bar Sauma (13th ct), a highly ranked Nestorian at some point distributed all his property to the poor.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence of an institution for the so-called 'official' help to the poor. However, members of local communities use to help each other, regardless of religion.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no research on that question, but it is most probable that families and relatives were the most responsible for the care of the elderly and infirm.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Initially, there were two schools that provided formal education to Christians: School of Edessa and School of Nisibis. Later on, in the 13th and 14th centuries, the Nestorians had a school near Lake Issik-Köl which was most probably attached to a Nestorian monastery.

Reference: Becker, Adam H.. Fear of God and the Beginning of Wisdom. University of Pennsylvania Press, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=KGGYAgAAQBAJ>.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: There were teachers who were not members of the clergy, although the clergy dominated. The position of a teacher was highly estimated. The major issue members of the Nestorian Christian community during the Mongol period had was the lack of knowledge about the non-Christian environment.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: For example, during the Mongol period, Khubilai was interested in raising educational standards to the members of the Nestorian community.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Reference: Halbertsma, Tjalling H. F.. *Early Christian Remains of Inner Mongolia*. BRILL, 2015. https://books.google.com/books/about/Early_Christian_Remains_of_Inner_Mongoli.html?hl=&id=tR2oBgAAQBAJ.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: There is no formal bureaucracy in the modern sense of that term. There is ecclesiastical and socio-cultural hierarchy within the group which is highly respected.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: There is no data about public food storage, but mutual help in providing food did exist. Despite of all differences and sometimes animosities, there seems to have been mutual help between the Christians of different denominations and other members of local communities in a given period.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Reference: Klimkeit, Hans-Joachim. *Religionsbegegnung Und Kulturaustausch in Asien*. Otto Harrassowitz Verlag, 2002. https://books.google.com/books/about/Religionsbegegnung_und_Kulturaustausch_i.html?hl=&id=x8b65_oP7g4C.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: There is no research on that question.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The Bar Shabba-fragment (initially written in Syriac) a Sogdian text found in Turfan mentions a great king who converted to Christianity and organized help for the people. It does not explicitly mention water, but one can strongly presume that as well as a form of help.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Notes: For example, John of Cora (14th ct) in his Book of the Estate of the Great Khan writes about the organized transport system and economy in China.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. Christians in Asia Before 1500. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: yes, especially in China which had the organized transport and economy.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: For example, in the Mongol period, Nestorian Christians were exempt from taxes according to a decree of Jinghis Khan. On the other hand, in a text from the Tang period (China) speaks about Christian monks who "must all be compelled to return to lay life and resume their original callings and pay taxes, or if they are foreigners they shall be sent back to their native places" The latter does not seem to have been a law, but it certainly demonstrates the spirit of the environment.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: For example, many Nestorian Christians served in the Mongol army.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: No, but Christian behavior is observed by ecclesiastical authorities.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: There is no research on that question.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: Many Christian churches (including the Nestorian community) had a law code that applied to all of its members. It included not only clergy but also all of its members. The laws covered both doctrinal (Scripture and theology) and everyday questions (inheritances, contracts, marriage etc.).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Especially in China and Mongolia. Their existence and freedom of preaching were dependent on the laws of the ruling dynasty. On top of that, members of the community served the army (e.g. in the Mongolian Empire).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: Community members are usually a part of a larger community where they serve the army.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Notes: Nestorian Christians use Syriac language and script by default. They also used local languages (e.g. Sogdian, Chinese, Mongolian), but Syriac remained the default language.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: Although religious leaders, monks and nuns are much more likely to be literate [in a written form of the language] than the wider population. Syriac was the language of the community members and the language used in the liturgy, but many Syriac texts were also translated into local languages. For example, there is a Pahlavi Psalter which was used in the liturgy.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: For example Parthian, Sogdian, Uighur (Old Turkic) or Middle Persian.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, they are also acquainted with local languages like Chinese, Mongolian, Persian, Sogdian, and Arabic. The texts they wrote were in various Central Asian languages. These texts were not only Christian, but also Manichaean and Chinese documents of secular nature.

Reference: Gilman, Ian, and Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. *Christians in Asia Before 1500*. Routledge, 2013. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=UGpr2KsbS94C>.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general

populace)

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: Nestorian (i.e. Eastern) Christians used the lunar Syrian months with the lunisolar year, most probably according to the Babylonian calendar and also the Syro-Macedonian calendar with the Syrian month-names. They were also acquainted with the Persian system of time reckoning and used Persian nomenclature as well.

Reference: Taqizadeh, S. H.. "The Iranian Festivals Adopted by the Christians and Condemned by the Jews". *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies*, July 13, 1940.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In the Persian Empire, China, Mongolia or India - religious practices of Nestorian Christians mingled with local cultural and political aspects which are reflected in their calendar.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no research on that question, but one can presume that families and communities were producing food for themselves: dairy products, camels, sheep, goats, oxen, and the like.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 5 CE - 14 CE

Status of Participants: Elite Religious Specialists Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: Because of the Silk Route, the diet of the members of the community was also influenced by their nomadic way of life.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: Elite Religious Specialists Non-elite (common people, general populace)

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